

Use case 1									
Exp Scenarios		5							
Scenarios found	Real Scenarios f	False Scenarios f	Missing scenario	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall	
Custom	5	5	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	5	5	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Multi-Stage LLV	5	5	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Hybrid	5	5	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

Test Case steps in valid scenari									
test case 0									
Exp Steps		3							
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall	
Custom	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Multi-Stage LLV	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Hybrid	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

test case 1									
Exp Steps		2							
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall	
Custom	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Multi-Stage LLV	3	2	1	0	0,666666667	0,333333333	1	0,666666667	1
Hybrid	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

test case 2									
Exp Steps		2							
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall	
Custom	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Multi-Stage LLV	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Hybrid	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

test case 3									
Exp Steps		1							
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall	
Custom	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Multi-Stage LLV	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Hybrid	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

test case 4									
Exp Steps		3							
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall	
Custom	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Multi-Stage LLV	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Hybrid	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

Averages for step Proportion Valid Proportion Invali Coverage Precision Recall

					Custom	1	0	1	1	1
					Single-Stage LL	1	0	1	1	1
					Multi-Stage LLM	0,933333333	0,066666667	1	0,933333333	1
					Hybrid	1	0	1	1	1
					Median for steps	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall
					Custom	1	0	1	1	1
					Single-Stage LL	1	0	1	1	1
					Multi-Stage LLM	1	0	1	1	1
					Hybrid	1	0	1	1	1

Fields Validity in Valid Steps																			
	Nbr Correct Op	Nbr Incorrect Op	Correct Operatio	Correct Protocol	Incorrect protoco	Correct Protocol	Correct Methods	Incorrect Method	Correct Method	Correct Compon	Incorrect Compo	Correct compon	Valid Inputs	Invalid Inputs	Valid Inputs Proj	Correct Expectat	Incorrect Expect	Correct Expectations	Proportion
Custom	11	0	1	11	0	1	11	0	1	11	0	1	10	1	0,90909091	11	0	1	
Single-Stage LL	11	0	1	11	0	1	11	0	1	11	0	1	11	0	1	11	0	1	
Multi-Stage LLM	11	0	1	11	0	1	11	0	1	11	0	1	11	0	1	9	2	0,818181818	
Hybrid	11	0	1	11	0	1	11	0	1	11	0	1	19	1	0,95	11	0	1	

Use case 2										
Exp Scenarios		7								
Scenarios found	Real Scenarios f	False Scenarios f	Missing scenario	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall		
Custom	7	7	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	7	7	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Multi-Stage LLV	7	6	1	1	0,857142857	0,142857143	0,857142857	0,857142857	0,857142857	0,857142857
Hybrid	7	7	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1

test case steps in valid scenari										
test case 0										
Exp Steps		3								
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall		
Custom	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Multi-Stage LLV	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Hybrid	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1

test case 1										
Exp Steps		2								
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall		
Custom	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	2	1	1	1	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
Multi-Stage LLV	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Hybrid	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1

test case 2										
Exp Steps		2								
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall		
Custom	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	1	1	0	1	1	0	0,5	1	1	0,5
Multi-Stage LLV	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Hybrid	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1

test case 3										
Exp Steps		1								
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall		
Custom	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Multi-Stage LLV	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Hybrid	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1

test case 4										
Exp Steps		3								
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall		
Custom	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	1	1	0	2	1	0	0,333333333	1	0,333333333	0,333333333
Multi-Stage LLV	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Hybrid	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1

test case 5										
Exp Steps		3								
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall		
Custom	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	1	1	0	2	1	0	0,333333333	1	0,333333333	0,333333333

Multi-Stage LLN	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Hybrid	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
test case 6										
Exp Steps	3									
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall		
Custom	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Single-Stage LLN	1	1	0	2	1	0	0,3333333333	1	0,3333333333	
Multi-Stage LLN NA	NA		#VALEUR!	#VALEUR!	#VALEUR!	#VALEUR!	#VALEUR!	#VALEUR!	#VALEUR!	
Hybrid	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Averages for step										
Custom	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Single-Stage LLN	0,928571429	0,071428571	0,571428571	0,928571429	0,571428571	0,928571429	0,571428571	0,928571429	0,571428571	
Multi-Stage LLN	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Hybrid	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Median for steps										
Custom	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Single-Stage LLN	1	0	0,416666667	1	0,416666667	1	0,416666667	1	0,416666667	
Multi-Stage LLN	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Hybrid	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Fields Validity in Valid Steps																			
	Nbr Correct Op	Nbr Incorrect Op	Correct Operatio	Correct Protocol	Incorrect protoco	Correct Protocol	Correct Methods	Incorrect Method	Correct Method	Correct Compon	Incorrect Compo	Correct compone	Valid Inputs	Invalid Inputs	Valid Inputs Proj	Correct Expectat	Incorrect Expect	Correct Expectations	Proportion
Custom	17	0	1	17	0	1	17	0	1	17	0	1	12	5	0,705882353	17	0	1	
Single-Stage LLN	8	0	1	8	0	1	8	0	1	8	0	1	8	0	1	8	0	1	
Multi-Stage LLN	14	0	1	14	0	1	14	0	1	14	0	1	14	0	1	14	0	1	
Hybrid	17	0	1	17	0	1	17	0	1	17	0	1	16	1	0,941176471	17	0	1	

Use case 3									
Exp Scenarios		5							
Scenarios found	Real Scenarios f	False Scenarios f	Missing scenario	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall	
Custom	5	5	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	5	5	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Multi-Stage LLN	5	5	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Hybrid	5	5	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

Payload steps in valid scenarios									
payload 0									
Exp Steps		3							
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall	
Custom	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Multi-Stage LLN	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Hybrid	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

payload 1									
Exp Steps		2							
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall	
Custom	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Multi-Stage LLN	3	2	1	0	0,666666667	0,333333333	1	0,666666667	1
Hybrid	2	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

payload 2									
Exp Steps		1							
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall	
Custom	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Multi-Stage LLN	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Hybrid	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

payload 3									
Exp Steps		3							
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall	
Custom	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	1	1	0	2	1	0	0,333333333	1	0,333333333
Multi-Stage LLN	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Hybrid	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

payload 4									
Exp Steps		3							
Steps found	Real Steps found	False Steps found	Missing Steps (F	Proportion Valid	Proportion Invali	Coverage	Precision	Recall	
Custom	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Single-Stage LL	1	1	0	2	1	0	0,333333333	1	0,333333333
Multi-Stage LLN	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
Hybrid	3	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1

Averages for step Proportion Valid Proportion Invali Coverage Precision Recall

		Averages						
			Proportion Valid	Proportion Invalid	Scenarios Covered	Scenarios Precision	Scenarios Recall	
Scenario coverage (Scenario Evaluation)		Custom	1	0	1	1	1	
		Single-Stage LLM	1	0	1	1	1	
		Multi-Stage LLM	0,952380952	0,047619048	0,952380952	0,952380952	0,952380952	
		Hybrid	1	0	1	1	1	
			Proportion Valid	Proportion Invalid	Payload steps Covered	Payload steps Precision	Payload steps Recall	
Correctness of generated tests (Step)	Average	Custom	1	0	1	1	1	
		Single-Stage LLM	0,976190476	0,023809524	0,768253968	0,976190476	0,768253968	
		Multi-Stage LLM	0,955555556	0,044444444	1	0,955555556	1	
		Hybrid	1	0	1	1	1	
Average of median		Custom	1	0	1	1	1	
		Single-Stage LLM	1	0	0,694444444	1	0,694444444	
		Multi-Stage LLM	1	0	1	1	1	
		Hybrid	1	0	1	1	1	
			Correct Operation	Correct Protocol	Correct Method	Correct components	Valid Inputs Proportion	Correct Expectations Proportion
Correctness of each step (Fields Evaluation)		Custom	1	1	1	1	0,871657754	1
		Single-Stage LLM	1	1	1	1	1	1
		Multi-Stage LLM	1	1	1	1	1	0,911616162
		Hybrid	1	1	1	1	0,96372549	1